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Role of magnetic ordering on transformation properties of Heusler Ni₂MnGa magnetic shape memory alloy

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Abstract

We pursued a theoretical investigation of the Ni-Mn-Ga Heusler alloy to understand the role of magnetism on the lattice stability and, consequently, the magnetic shape memory (MSM) effect. Two *ab initio* methods were used for the calculations: the widely used standard density functional theory (DFT) and the advanced quasiparticle self-consistent *GW* (QSGW) method. The latter is expected to be more accurate due to the explicit inclusion of electron correlation. The generalized susceptibility calculated by QSGW indicated that the existence of magnetic ordering in the high temperature phase, austenite, is crucial for the formation of the modulated martensites. The ferromagnetic austenite transforms into modulated martensites that can exhibit MSM, but the paramagnetic austenite does not possess this tendency in accordance with experimental observations. In the non-modulated tetragonal martensite (NM), we investigated the role of magnetic ordering on the stability of the lattice and twinning interface. We found that the elastic constants remain unchanged during magnetic moment rotation, confirming the stability of NM in agreement with the notion that it is a ground state. Furthermore, the calculation revealed that the magnetization rotation has a negligible influence on the stability of the twinning interface in NM

1 Introduction

The magnetic shape memory (MSM) effect was discovered in Ni-Mn-Ga by Ullakko in 1996 [1]. Even though the effect has also been observed in other materials, e.g., Fe-Pt [2], Fe-Pd [3], and even in antiferromagnetic or paramagnetic (PM) materials, Ni-Mn-Ga is still the most promising MSM material. Ni-Mn-Ga is intensively studied to understand the essence of the MSM effect and what properties are required from materials to exhibit the MSM effect. Thus, the search for other MSM materials could be done based on these criteria. Moreover, compounds derived from Ni-Mn-Ga (doped or substituted) are investigated as MSM candidate materials, because the main issue of Ni-Mn-Ga is the low transformation temperature to martensite (T_M) and Curie temperature (T_C), complicating the applications of this unique material. The substitution of Ga by elements with the same number of valence electrons, i.e., Al, In, or their combination, has been investigated theoretically [4] and experimentally [5–7] to improve the ductility and application temperature range.

The formation of the modulated phases is probably one of the essential aspects of MSM since the effect has been observed only for modulated 10M and 14M phases in Ni-Mn-Ga. 10M and 14M phases exhibit the high twin boundary mobility compared to non-modulated (NM) martensite. However, the origin of this high mobility in 10M/14M is unclear; it is unknown why NM exhibits higher twinning stress and lower mobility compared to modulated structures and subsequently why NM do not exhibit MSM. The only exception is Ni-Mn-Ga doped by Co and Cu, which exhibits

large field induced strain in the NM phase [8]. However, it was later shown that such material is on the edge of modulation instability [9].

Therefore, the ability to predict the formation of the modulated phases is important for the search for MSM candidate materials. The possibility of creating the modulation is indicated by calculations of the generalized susceptibility, which can reveal the system instability, originating from the electronic structure. Furthermore, the experiments indicate that the magnetic ordering can be crucial for the formation of the modulated structures since the modulated structures occur only for compositions where the transition to the ferromagnetic (FM) state occurs in austenite and subsequently the transformation to martensite occurs, i.e., the Curie temperature is higher than the martensitic transformation temperature $T_C > T_M$. Several theoretical studies indicated that the wavevector of the soft phonon mode in austenite depends significantly on magnetic state [10] and magnetization [11–13].

The calculated generalized susceptibility $\chi(\mathbf{q})$ considering only the Fermi surface nesting (FSN) can indicate the structural instability originating from phonon instability caused by the strong interaction of the given phonon with the electronic structure [14], resulting in atomic displacements. $\chi(\mathbf{q})$ identifies wave vectors \mathbf{q} where electron scattering is enhanced, indicating possible atomic modulations that require lower energy due to FSN. Several theoretical studies using different approaches were published. First, DFT calculation using LDA was performed, observing a singularity of the generalized susceptibility for $\mathbf{q} = 2\pi/a(\xi, \xi, 0)$ and $\xi = 0.42$ [10]. This \mathbf{q} was assigned to 10M phase, since it seems to predict correctly the experimentally measured modulated 10M structure with $q = 0.402$ and $\mathbf{q} = (q, q, 0)$ [15]. The experimental value corresponds to 5-atomic layers without considering their occupation by individual elements. However, the calculated \mathbf{q} vector by DFT provides only the information about the long-range periodicity, but no information about the internal stacking sequence. Thus, the comparison between calculation and experiment is not straightforward.

Later, GGA calculation observed the singularity for a different \mathbf{q} vector [11] with similar results as LDA calculation. However, since GGA predicts 4O phase (corresponding to $\xi = 0.5$ and $\mathbf{q} = 2\pi/a(\xi, \xi, 0)$) to be the ground state [16], this possibly impacts the electronic structures, resulting in the observed calculated \mathbf{q} vector. Baigutlin et al. [17] used the SCAN meta-GGA functional containing the self-interaction corrections, behaving effectively as a GGA+U calculation with $U \approx 2$ eV on Mn atoms. Using the SCAN functional results in differences of the Fermi surface and subsequently, different singularities of the generalized susceptibility (FSN vectors parameters are $\xi_1 = 0.263 \approx 2/7$ and $\xi_2 = 0.784$, where $\mathbf{q} = 2\pi/a(\xi, \xi, 0)$) [17].

The more accurate quasiparticle self-consistent GW (QSGW) method was utilized for the electronic structure calculation and the generalized susceptibility with the corresponding FSN vector $\mathbf{q} = 2\pi/a(\xi, \xi, 0)$ and $\xi = 0.2$ [18]. This $\xi = 0.2$ is supposed to be the nesting vector corresponding to five-period (10-atomic layers) structures such as 10M, since that is the long-range periodicity considering the atomic occupation. The QSGW method shows an energetic preference for long-period modulations in contrast to GGA. Recent experimental studies have supported this result, as the modulated 10M structure for all Ni-Mn-Ga compositions shows modulation evolution with temperature [15] and then follows a complete or incomplete sequence of martensite phases during cooling: 10M commensurate – 10M incommensurate (up to $\mathbf{q} = 3/7$) – modulated 14M ($\mathbf{q} = 2/7$) – NM [19]. From experiments it seems that longer-period modulations (such as 14M) are energetically preferred over 10M, which is stabilized by a lower free energy at higher temperatures. The QSGW calculations using the magnetic rigid band model proved to be more consistent with these experimental observations and to predict the intrinsic instability of austenite and its strong dependence on the Fermi surface in Ni-Mn-Ga modified by doping [18]. However, it is not possible to determine what composition would correspond to the results of such simple model. Recently, we reported a comparison of the electronic structures and the generalized susceptibilities of three Heusler alloys Ni_2MnX ($X = \text{Al, Ga, In}$) using QSGW, DFT and DFT+U methods [4]. The observed differences among these three compounds in the FSN vector ($\mathbf{q} = 2\pi/a(\xi, \xi, 0)$ and $\xi \approx 0.2$) and Fermi surface calculated by QSGW correspond well with the differences in the experimental behavior. Especially, the peak for Ni_2MnGa is significantly higher compared to the other two compounds [4].

Remaining unanswered question is, what is the role of magnetic order on stability of martensitic phases in Ni-Mn-Ga. Three aspects related to the MSM effect, which may be affected by magnetism, are investigated in this work; what the role does magnetism play in the formation of the modulated phases essential for MSM effect, can the rotation of the magnetic moments destabilize the NM structure creating a path to modulated structure and can the magnetic moment rotation destabilize compound twin interface and increase its mobility paving a path to magnetic

shape memory effect? We used the generalized susceptibility as a theoretical tool that can provide some insight to these questions.

2 Computational setting

The projected augmented wave (PAW) method [20] implemented in the Vienna Ab initio Simulation package (VASP) [21–24] code is utilized for describing the core electrons and for the DFT calculations. All calculations have been performed using Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof exchange and correlation functional [25]. The magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy (MAE) and elastic constants of NM with magnetic moments oriented in an easy $[100]_{\text{NM}}$ (or $[010]_{\text{NM}}$) direction and hard axis $[001]_{\text{NM}}$ direction are calculated in this work. The magneto-crystalline anisotropy is also expressed as an effective magnetic field (anisotropy magnetic field) B_{MAE} required to turn the magnetic moments to the specific direction (hard axis) from the easy axis directions is calculated based on the Zeeman energy relation:

$$B_{\text{MAE}} = \frac{2E_{\text{MAE}}}{M}, \quad (1)$$

where M is the total magnetic moment and E_{MAE} is the magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy with respect to the easy axis direction.

For all Ni_2MnGa calculations of NM, we used the noncollinear version (NC) of VASP, which also requires spin-orbit interaction (SOI) [26] to be included to allow changing the direction of magnetic moments. These calculations have been performed on the primitive cell with the cutoff energy 800 eV and $18 \times 18 \times 18$ \mathbf{k} -mesh. The geometry optimization of the computational cell is done as the first step. The valence electrons included for each element are $3p$, $3d$ and $4s$ for Ni and Mn, and $3d$, $4s$ and $4p$ for Ga. The convergence condition for the self-consistent cycle is 10^{-8} eV and for the geometry optimization is 10^{-7} eV. The geometry optimizations were performed using the Methfessel-Paxton method [27] of order 2 to determine the partial occupancies $f_{n\mathbf{k}}$ for each orbital with the width of the smearing 0.2 eV. The tetrahedron method is used for the high-accuracy calculation of the total internal energy. The direction of the magnetic moments is set by changing the global spin-quantization axis referring to the defined Cartesian coordinates.

The elastic constants can be calculated from the stress acting on the computational cell or an analysis of the calculated total energy of a cell as a function of applied strain. The first approach requires accurate stress calculations, i.e., it is more computationally costly [28]. The second method is used in this work. Deformations of the structure based on the strain patterns allow to calculate the elastic constants of the system from the total internal energy calculated by the DFT calculations. The energy of the deformed cell can be expressed by a Taylor series expansion for small strain using Voigt notation as:

$$E(V, \varepsilon) = E(V_0, 0) + V_0 \sum_{i=1}^6 \sigma_i \varepsilon_i + \frac{V_0}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^6 c_{ij} \varepsilon_i \varepsilon_j + O(\varepsilon^3), \quad (2)$$

where V_0 is the volume of the undeformed cell and $E(V_0, 0)$ is the total internal energy of the undeformed cell. The body-centered tetragonal lattice has six independent elastic constants and cubic three. However, it is more convenient to use the shear modulus c' and c'_{bct} for cubic and tetragonal lattice, respectively. These shear modules are defined as:

$$c' = \frac{c_{11} - c_{12}}{2} \quad (3)$$

$$c'_{\text{bct}} = \frac{1}{6}(c_{11} + c_{12} + 2c_{33} - 4c_{13}). \quad (4)$$

The cubic constant c' typically softens when the temperature is approaching the austenite-martensite transition temperature. This softening indicates the instability of austenite to the Bain distortion, i.e., cubic to tetragonal distortion observed in many shape memory alloys. The measurements of the thermal evolution of the elastic constants can be used to identify the phase transition. Thus calculations of c' can provide insight into the instability of austenite. The soft shear elastic constant c'_{bct} is in tetragonal martensite also connected to the Bain distortion and its decrease can indicate the destabilization of tetragonal lattice.

The electronic susceptibility, which originates from matrix elements of electron-phonon interaction and Fermi surface nesting (FSN), can be used to investigate the effects of atomic displacements on phase stability. These contributions are part of the long-range atomic forces that

Table 1. Magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy calculated for different directions of the magnetization of the tetragonal non-modulated (NM) martensite. B_{MAE} is the expected value of the external magnetic field calculated by Eq. (1) necessary to rotate the magnetization in this direction.

	<i>ab</i> -plane			<i>ac</i> -plane			Ref. [39]	Ref. [41]
	$[100]_{\text{NM}}$	$[210]_{\text{NM}}$	$[110]_{\text{NM}}$	$[100]_{\text{NM}}$	$[101]_{\text{NM}}$	$[001]_{\text{NM}}$		
MAE [$\mu\text{eV}/\text{f.u.}$]	0	1.40	10.91	0	108.2	322.0	311.0	700.0
B_{MAE} [T]	0	0.012	0.093	0	0.919	2.737	-	-

may result in the formation of modulation (for more details see Ref. [14]). In this work only the FSN contribution is investigated as it was shown that this is probably the main contribution, causing the formation of the modulated phases [4, 10, 11, 17, 18]. Considering only the FSN part, the part (generalized susceptibility) of the electronic susceptibility is as follows:

$$\chi(\mathbf{q}) = \frac{1}{N_{\mathbf{k}}} \sum_{m,n,\mathbf{k},\sigma} \frac{f(\epsilon_{n\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}}^{\sigma}) - f(\epsilon_{m\mathbf{k}}^{\sigma})}{\epsilon_{m\mathbf{k}}^{\sigma} - \epsilon_{n\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}}^{\sigma}}, \quad (5)$$

where $N_{\mathbf{k}}$ is the number of \mathbf{k} -points in the 1st Brillouin zone, and $\epsilon_{m\mathbf{k}}^{\sigma}$ and $f(\epsilon_{m\mathbf{k}}^{\sigma})$ are the eigenvalue and Fermi-Dirac distribution function, for the electronic state represented by the band index m , wavevector \mathbf{k} , and spin index σ . If the condition of FSN is satisfied, i.e., one of the levels $\epsilon_{m\mathbf{k}}^{\sigma}$ and $\epsilon_{n\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}}^{\sigma}$ is unoccupied and the corresponding energies of these states are comparable, i.e., $\epsilon_{m\mathbf{k}}^{\sigma} \approx \epsilon_{n\mathbf{k}+\mathbf{q}}^{\sigma}$, then $\chi(\mathbf{q})$ has a singularity with high value. This singularity indicates the system instability that may result in the formation of the modulation specified by wave vector for which the large value of $\chi(\mathbf{q})$ occurs.

Calculations of the generalized susceptibility have been performed using the ecalj package [29] that utilizes an all-electron mixed basis using the highly localized muffin-tin (LMT) orbitals and augmented plane waves (APWs) with optimised parameters for numerical stability [30]. The angular orbitals were taken up to $\ell = 3$, and the cutoff of the APW basis set is 3 Ry. This relatively small cutoff is used because the main part of the basis consists of the LMT orbitals, and the APW basis is auxiliary. Two methods have been used: the DFT method and the quasi-particle self-consistent GW (QSGW) method [31–34]. The QSGW method is a many-body perturbation theory method, improving the calculation accuracy over the standard DFT method. GW approximation is utilized to determine the exchange and correlation potential in the self-consistent approach by calculating the self-energy from the GW method and using the self-energy to calculate the exchange and correlation potential. The calculations have been performed for non-spin polarized (NMAG) and spin-polarized [4] cases to investigate the role of magnetism in austenite to create modulated phases.

In the QSGW framework, $16 \times 16 \times 16$ \mathbf{k} -grids are used for the DFT loop and $8 \times 8 \times 8$ \mathbf{k} -grids are employed for the GW loop in the self-energy calculation. The exchange and correlation potentials for a specific \mathbf{k} -point are interpolated in the Brillouin zone [34]. The convergence criterion for a self-consistent cycle of QSGW calculation is 1 meV change of eigenvalues. The generalized susceptibility $\chi(\mathbf{q})$ is calculated on a $192 \times 192 \times 192$ \mathbf{k} -grid in the cubic Brillouin zone that has a volume twice that of the first Brillouin zone. The calculations have been performed on the primitive FCC cell with the experimental lattice constant 5.825 Å. This lattice constant is used due to the current limitation of the QSGW method, which currently does not provide the total internal energy, making geometry optimization impossible. Concerned about the details of computation parameters, refer to the references [29, 34].

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Magnetic properties

At first, we considered the calculation of the stability of the tetragonal NM phase with the c/a ratio = 1.26 against the magnetic moments rotation. Calculated total magnetic moment M was 4.07 $\mu_{\text{B}}/\text{f.u.}$, which is similar to other DFT calculations (4.16 $\mu_{\text{B}}/\text{f.u.}$ [35] and 4.09 $\mu_{\text{B}}/\text{f.u.}$ [36]). The experimental total magnetic moment of stoichiometric martensite is 4.12 - 4.17 $\mu_{\text{B}}/\text{f.u.}$ at 0 K [37, 38]. Further, we calculated magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy (MAE) i.e., the energy difference between $[100]_{\text{NM}}$ (easy axis) and $[001]_{\text{NM}}$ (hard axis) directions. We obtained a value of 322 $\mu\text{eV}/\text{f.u.}$ which is in good agreement with the previous theoretical results [39–41].

The calculations of MAE by Enkovaara et al. [40], with a computed value of MAE \approx 180 $\mu\text{eV}/\text{f.u.}$, is not listed in the table as the MAE value differs from the calculations in this work due to

the different structure of martensite, considering a tetragonal structure with the c/a ratio = 0.94. This corresponds to experimental consideration of the martensitic structure as pseudotetragonal before the modulation was included, as it was usual in the onset of MSM research.

Our MAE calculation in ab -plane indicates that $[100]_{\text{NM}}$ direction is preferable over $[110]_{\text{NM}}$ direction (Tabel 1). However, the energy difference is only $10.9 \mu\text{eV}/\text{f.u.}$, corresponding to a 0.093 T magnetic field in Ni_2MnGa , indicating that the ab -plane can be considered an easy plane. In contrast, the corresponding magnetic field required to rotate the magnetic moments from $[100]_{\text{NM}}$ to $[001]_{\text{NM}}$ is $\approx 2.74 \text{ T}$ in Ni_2MnGa . That is a significantly higher magnetic field than the experimental one, which is $\approx 0.7 \text{ T}$ at room temperature [42], but for off-stoichiometric material with Mn excess. Moreover, the twinned structure was not initially considered, and revised measurements on a single martensite variant gave an anisotropy field of $\approx 1.5 \text{ T}$ at 10 K for the $\text{Ni}_{50.5}\text{Mn}_{30.4}\text{Ga}_{19.1}$ sample [43].

There are several possible explanations for the differences between theoretical and experimental MAE values. As mentioned above, there is an issue of temperature since calculations are done for 0 K , but the experiments are done at a specific temperature and composition, which is not stoichiometric, and the NM phase occurs in the material with an excess of Mn or Ni [37], while the calculation was made on the stoichiometric NM phase. The excess Mn will introduce antiferromagnetic ordering [42], which can affect the measured anisotropy. In fact, experimentally, the stoichiometric Ni_2MnGa martensite exhibits the 10M modulated structure down to the lowest temperature.

Several published studies calculated MAE or magnetocrystalline anisotropy (MCA) for off-stoichiometric and doped systems. Enkovaara et al.[40] suggested that the strong MCA originates from the nonsymmetric surrounding of Ni atoms with a maximum in stoichiometric Ni_2MnGa [40, 44]. The same is observed in the doped systems, i.e., a decrease of MAE (MCA) with increasing the concentration of dopant [40, 41, 44–47]. Thus we can expect that experimental value of anisotropy to be lower than calculated as the anisotropy can be experimentally determined only in quite strong off-stoichiometric composition in contrast to stoichiometric calculation. Our result of the anisotropy field for stoichiometric composition compared to the experimental off-stoichiometric composition corresponds well with such observations.

However, several other effects can contribute to the MAE temperature dependence that are not included in the DFT calculations. These contributions are from electronic states, magnons and phonons [40] or other contributions such as from shape anisotropy, orbital magnetization, change of the density of states due to the Berry curvature and external field [48]. Additionally, Zelený et al. [49] showed that the DFT+U method can modify the potential energy surface and the energy sequence of phases and thus, including Hubbard correction U may also be necessary for a reproduction of the experimental MAE.

3.2 Elastic properties

The elastic constants for the NM phase calculated in this work are similar to those previously reported by Kart et al. [50]. However, the experimental elastic constants c_{11} , c' and c'_{bct} are significantly lower compared to the calculated one. The remaining ones are in relatively good agreement. Koubský et al. [51] showed that c_{11} , c_{44} and c' values can be reproduced by the DFT+U method, but Hubbard U parameters affected also some other elastic constants, resulting in a significant difference from the experimental value, e.g., c'_{bct} or c_{66} .

Importantly, the elastic constants are marginally influenced by the magnetization orientation (Table 2). The elastic constants for standard calculation, where all the magnetic moments are projected into the z -direction, are slightly different compared to the elastic constants for magnetization in the direction of the easy and hard axes. Moreover, the elastic constants for the NM phase are almost identical for both the easy axis $[100]_{\text{NM}}$ and the hard axis $[001]_{\text{NM}}$. The differences vary from 0.1 to 0.4 GPa , and no dependence on the magnetization orientation is evident (Table 2). The elastic constants are calculated from the total internal energies, and the changes in the total internal energies caused by the structural deformations are in the range of $10 \text{ meV}/\text{f.u.}$, and MAE is only $0.3 \text{ meV}/\text{f.u.}$. Thus, the MAE contribution to the total internal energy does not provide a significant change to the calculated elastic constants, and thus, the NM phase is stable independently of the orientation of the magnetic moment, and it is not destabilized by magnetization rotation.

3.3 Twinning path

A similar low influence of the magnetic moment orientation was found during the calculation of the twinning path (Fig. 1) in NM martensite. This described the effect of changing the magnetization

Table 2. Elastic constants calculated by DFT for Ni₂MnGa nonmodulated (NM) martensite for different orientations of the magnetization and published experimental at room temperature and theoretical elastic constants; SOI means spin-orbit interaction was included in calculation; NC means the noncollinear implementation of VASP code was used.

method	Elastic constants [GPa]								
	c_{11}	c_{12}	c_{13}	c_{33}	c_{44}	c_{66}	c'	c'_{bct}	
hard axis [001] _{NM} DFT with SOI	250.7	72.9	142.5	196.0	101.8	56.9	88.9	24.3	
easy axis [100] _{NM} NC DFT with SOI	251.8	72.8	143.1	197.2	101.7	56.5	89.5	25.1	
hard axis [001] _{NM} NC DFT with SOI	251.5	72.9	142.9	196.8	101.6	56.5	89.3	24.4	
Experimental at RT Ref. [52]	197.8	60.9	143.5	189.1	106.2	49.7	62.5	12.9	
Theoretical Ref. [50]	252	74	144	194	100	55	89	23	
Theoretical Ref. [51]	201.3	75.3	106.7	174.5	102.7	70.7	63.0	33.1	

direction on the twinning interface. Generally, the magnetization has to continuously rotate from the easy axis in one variant to the easy axis in the other variant. The important question is whether such rotation destabilizes the twinning interface (boundary) connecting two differently oriented variants. If so, it may contribute to the high mobility of the a/c twin boundaries, which are extremely mobile in modulated martensites.

The energy profiles are calculated along the twinning path (Fig. 1) between two differently oriented variants of NM for different directions of magnetic moments within the coordinate system (x_1 , x_2 , x_3) in Fig. 1. In the calculation the magnetic moments have been oriented along [001] axis where none of the variants is preferable, along [110] where variant (e) is preferable, and along [1 $\bar{1}$ 0] where variant (a) is preferable considering magnetocrystalline anisotropy.

The energy barriers (Fig. 2) are almost identical for all three different orientations of the magnetization, indicating that the magnetic field may not have a significant influence on the stability of the martensitic phase around the a/c twin boundary. However, it is also important to mention that the deformed structure has not been optimized, and thus, the energy barrier is the upper limit for the actual one. On the other hand, the change of the structure should be minimal since the structure can only change in the x_1 direction to comply with the compatibility condition. The result shows that the magnetization direction has a negligible influence on the depth of the minima and the height of the energy barrier. The differences among the different orientations of magnetization are minimal. Although the strong magnetic anisotropy is needed for magnetically induced reorientation (MIR) effect, our calculation suggest that in NM (tetragonal) martensite the rotation of magnetic moments out of the easy direction cannot facilitate the motion of the twinning interface.

3.4 Generalized susceptibility

To investigate the role of magnetism in the formation of the modulated phase in martensitic transformation from cubic austenite, the generalized susceptibility (Fig. 3) was calculated for FM (ferromagnetic ordering) and NMAG (non-spin polarized state). The NMAG calculation can be considered a simple model of the PM state since random magnetic disorder is impossible to include in the conventional DFT or QSGW calculation. As was shown in the previous works [4, 18], DFT is not an accurate method for this type of calculation and more advanced methods is to be used for more accurate results. The QSGW method seems to reliably predict the formation of the modulated phases.

Figure 1. The twinning path between two differently oriented NM cells, (a) and (e) are the undeformed NM cells, and (b), (c) and (d) are deformed cells.

Previous research [4, 18], revealed that there is a sharp peak of the generalized susceptibility for the FSN vector around $2\pi/a(0.2, 0.2, 0)$ for QSGW and $2\pi/a(0.4, 0.4, 0)$ for DFT in FM Ni₂MnGa (see Fig. 3). This behavior originates from the significant differences between Fermi surfaces calculated by QSGW or DFT due to different amount of the parallel portions of the Fermi surfaces [4]. These parallel part of the Fermi surfaces contribute to FSN and thus, the generalized susceptibility. Since NMAG calculations result in significantly different Fermi surfaces for both QSGW and DFT compared to FM calculations (Fig. 4). Consequently, the peaks of generalized susceptibility disappear in our NMAG calculations, i.e., austenite in the NMAG state (or it may be assumed that in the PM state) is not susceptible to transformation to the modulated phase. Since this behavior is observed for both DFT and QSGW methods, this simple model of the PM state may be considered as accurate. This is the first theoretical indication that the magnetic ordering is crucial for the formation of the modulated phases. However, further conclusions are limited due to simplicity of our model, but several theoretical studies also used this simple approach [10, 53]. An improved representation of PM state may be required for more accurate results; the disordered local moment approach [54] or coherent potential approximation [55] may enhance the framework of the instability discussion. However, these methods are not currently feasible within the QSGW calculation.

4 Conclusions

Our calculation indicates that the elastic properties of Ni₂MnGa NM martensite are independent of the orientation of magnetic moments. Further, the orientation of the magnetization to the easy or hard axis does not significantly change the energy barrier of the twinning path between two variants of the NM phase, and thus it does not contribute to twin interface mobility. Although strong magnetocrystalline anisotropy is a necessary condition for magnetic shape memory effect or magnetically induced reorientation (MIR), calculations demonstrate that the atomic potentials are not affected by the rotation of magnetization from the easy axis to the hard axis in the NM phase. This suggests that the twinning mechanism of *a/c* twins in modulated martensites may also be unaffected when the magnetic moments are rotated during MIR. Moreover, the independence of the elastic constants indicates a small effect of spin-orbit coupling on the elastic properties.

In contrast, the existence of magnetic ordering has a crucial impact on the formation of the modulated martensitic phases. The generalized susceptibility calculated for the NMAG (non-spin polarized) state indicates significant changes of the Fermi surface, which does not support the formation of the modulated phases. On the other hand, if the austenite is in the FM state, the austenite phase is prone to the formation of modulated martensites upon transformation.

The results of the generalized susceptibility, together with the other results in this work, indicate that the role of the magnetic ordering is essential for the formation of the modulated phases in Ni-Mn-Ga. These results are consistent with experimental observations and provide another example of the correlation of the modulation formation in martensite with the calculated generalized susceptibility. Such observation can be essential for further research of the MSM effect and for a search of other materials exhibiting similar properties as Ni-Mn-Ga alloys. As well as stability discussion conducted by the free energy, the instability discussion presented here may play a role in the clarification of the physical mechanism among the phase diagram of MSM alloys.

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Data availability

Data are available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author.

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Figure 2. Energy profiles of the transformation path between two differently oriented NM cells for different magnetization directions in coordinate system from Fig. 1 ; magnetization is in [001] direction in [110] direction and in $[1\bar{1}0]$ direction; (a) – (e) are labels of the structure (see Fig. 1).

Figure 3. Comparison of the generalized susceptibility of austenite along the [110] direction in Ni_2MnGa calculated by DFT and QSGW method for ferromagnetic (FM) and non-spin polarized (NMAG).

Figure 4. Fermi surfaces for majority and minority spins for FM calculation and for NMAG calculation of Ni_2MnGa austenite by the QSGW method.